

Synthesis of 3-Anisyl-2-piperidylpropanol¹

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Synthesis of 3-anisyl-2-piperidylpropanol^a (I), characterised through its hydrochloride, m.p. 212°, is described.

Alangine A, m. p. 85°, $[\alpha]_D -41.3^\circ$ (CHCl₃), an alkaloid isolated from the root-bark of *Alangium lamarckii* Thw. (*Alangiaceae*), was proposed (Bhakuni *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, **19B**, 8) to have the structure (I). Its possible identity with alangine, m.p. 80°, $[\alpha]_D -34^\circ$ (CHCl₃), isolated from the same source (Chopra and Chowhan, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1934, **21**, 507), was also indicated. The arguments put forward in support of this structural assignment are not, however, very convincing. Since we have been actively interested in the field (Roy and Pakrashi, *Ann. Biochem. Exptl. Med.*, 1960, **20**, 103; Dutta and Pakrashi, *ibid.*, p. 279) for some time, we undertook and achieved the synthesis of (I) by the following route:

Anisylidenemalonic ester (II), prepared according to Knoevenagel (*Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 2594) was hydrogenated in ethanol over Adams' catalyst. Saponification of the product and purification by distillation and crystallisations from benzene afforded the corresponding saturated dicarboxylic acid (III) in flakes, m.p. 122° (uncorr.). Bromination of (III) followed by decarboxylation furnished 2-bromo-3-anisylpropionic acid (IV). The bromo-acid was condensed with piperidine, esterified, and reduced with LiAlH₄ to yield 3-anisyl-

2-piperidylpropanol¹ (I), isolated as hydrochloride in needles from acetone or benzene-methanol, m.p. 212° (uncorr.). The infrared absorption of the hydrochloride is reproduced in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

After the completion of our work we came across the reported synthesis (Kapil *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 136) of (I). The synthetic sample has been claimed to be different from alangine A without disclosing the mode of comparison. Any way, the above report necessitated the publication of the details of our work without having a chance to confirm the identity or non-identity of our compound with alangine A. Our method and data, however, differ from those of Kapil *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) in some important aspects (*vide* Experimental), the notable one being the melting point of the hydrochloride of the final product, which they report as 164°, whereas our sample melts at 212°.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Anisylidenemalonic Ester (II).—Freshly distilled anisaldehyde (40 g.) and malonic ester (49 g.) were mixed together with diethylamine (1 c.c.) and the mixture was left at room temperature for 10 days. The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for 6 hrs. and distilled. The fraction distilling at 206-208°/9 mm was collected; yield 26g. (32%).

Anisylmalonic Acid (III).—The preceding ester (II) (26 g.) was dissolved in ethanol, charcoaled, filtered directly in the reaction flask, and hydrogenated at ordinary pressure over Adams' catalyst (0.3 g.) (2.1 litres of hydrogen were taken up). The slurry was filtered, the filtrate freed of solvent, and distilled at 190-92°/9 mm; yield 25 g. (95.5%).

*All melting points are uncorrected. Analyses were done by Dr. A. Bernhardt, Max-Planck Institute, Mülheim (Ruhr), W. Germany and Dra. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford, England.

The total ester was added dropwise to a 50% ethanolic KOH (5 c.c.) and the solution was warmed on a water-bath for 4 hours, cooled, and poured in water (15 c.c.) containing crushed ice (15 g.). The solution was extracted with ether and the aqueous layer acidified with HCl (conc., pH 3-4) in suchwise that the temperature did not rise above 20°. The separated acid was extracted with ether, washed with water, dried (anhyd. Na₂SO₄), and concentrated. The oily residue on crystallisation from benzene afforded (III) in flakes, m.p. 122°, yield 16g. (80%). The aqueous portion was saturated with NaCl and extracted with ether; after the usual working up it gave a solid, m.p. 190-200°. It showed FeCl₃ coloration indicating that demethylation had occurred during strong alkaline hydrolysis. It was reconverted to the required anisylmalonic acid with Me₂SO₄ and KOH, the total yield of (III) being almost quantitative. (Found: C, 58.51; H, 5.46. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₂O₅: C, 58.93; H, 5.40%).

2-Bromo-3-anisylpropionic Acid (IV).—The dicarboxylic acid (III) (5.6 g.) was taken in dry ether and dry bromine (0.9 c.c., ~1.5M) was added dropwise with constant shaking till the solution became red-brown. It was left for $\frac{1}{4}$ hr. and stirred occasionally (cf. Fischer, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 3064). The ethereal solution was washed, dried (anhyd. Na₂SO₄), and the solvent distilled. The resulting brownish yellow viscous liquid (7 g.) was heated at ordinary pressure at 150-60° for 4 hours in an oil bath. A portion of the gummy brown mass was sublimed at 80-90°/0.01 mm as a low-melting solid.

Methyl 3-Anisyl-2-piperidylpropionate (V).—Treatment of a solution of the bromo-acid (IV) (5 g.) in ether with piperidine (3 g.) in the same solvent resulted in an immediate separation of an oil. It was either left for 10 days when the oil solidified in needles or refluxed for 4 hours on a water bath. The product was directly methylated with diazomethane. The ester was taken up in 2N-HCl, basified, and extracted with CHCl₃ in the conventional way to yield 4.8 g. (92%) of the crude material.

3-Anisyl-2-piperidylpropanol^a (I).—The ester (V) (2 g.) in dry ether (50 c.c.) was gradually added to a cooled and constantly stirred suspension of LiAlH₄ (6 g.) in ether (300 c.c.). The mixture was then refluxed for 4 hours on a water bath with stirring. The complex was decomposed with water and worked up to yield an oil (0.6 g., 26.5%). It was dissolved in ether (dry) with minimum amount of methanol and dry HCl gas was passed through the cooled solution. The hydrochloride was dissolved in hot water, treated with charcoal, and filtered. The filtrate was basified, extracted with ether, and the solvent removed. The base, thus obtained, was chromatographed over neutral alumina (E. Merck) in a column (12 × 1.4 cm) and eluted successively with petroleum ether, petroleum ether-benzene (1:1), benzene, and chloroform. Among the oily residues from the later fractions of benzene only those which responded to the alkaloidal tests were collected together, reconverted to hydrochloride, and crystallised from absolute ethanol-acetone in light colorless flakes (103 mg.), m.p. 200°. Recrystallisations from acetone and then from methanol-benzene yielded pure 3-anisyl-2-piperidylpropanol^a hydrochloride in small needles. (Found: C, 62.66; H, 8.71; N, 4.53. Calc. for C₁₅H₂₄O₂NCl: C, 63.03; H, 8.47; N, 4.91%). U.V. spectra in 95% EtOH: $\lambda_{\max}$ 276 (log ϵ 3.22) and 283 m μ (log ϵ 3.17); infrared (nujol mull) bands at 3337, 1623, 1525, 1312, 1265, 1189, 1170 and 1140 (shoulder), 1116, 1054, 1035, 998, 955, 938 (shoulder), 916, 815, 774 besides a broad split band between 855 and 840 cm⁻¹.

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